

Transferring Students with Behavioral Cases: A Solution or Desolation

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Abstract

The transfer of students with behavioral cases is a common strategy employed by schools to address persistent disciplinary challenges. While often regarded as a practical solution, this practice raises concerns about its effectiveness in fostering genuine behavioral improvement. This article examines whether student transfers serve as a constructive intervention or merely displace the problem to another institution. Drawing on interviews and observations, the study analyzes the academic, emotional, and social implications of transferring students with behavioral issues. Findings suggest that although transfers may provide immediate relief for the sending school, they often contribute to stigmatization, adjustment difficulties, and the perpetuation of behavioral struggles. The article argues for the adoption of inclusive and restorative approaches as more sustainable alternatives to exclusionary practices.

Keywords: behavioral cases, student transfer, school discipline, inclusion, restorative approaches

Chapter 1

INTRODUCTION

Situation Analysis

Students' misbehavior is a worldwide phenomenon that affects every school across the globe. Misbehavior may include excessive absences, disruptive talking, interfering with teaching activities, harassing classmates, verbal insults, rudeness to teacher, defiance, and hostility against fellow students and teachers (Caballes and Palma, 2022). Students' misbehavior presents a great challenge to the learning process which does not only interfere with teaching and learning but are also a leading contributor to teachers' stress (Walker, 2025).

No school is exempted from such challenges and problems. Every school year number of students undergo interrogation and investigation due to misbehaviors. Most often misbehaved students have not only undergone one conference but multiple times. Different school personnel like the teachers, advisers, year level coordinator, head teacher coordinator, guidance counselors, and sometimes even the principal cooperate to address students' misbehavior. Often times there are students whose offences escalated to an unmanageable level. As a result, schools implement measures to address the problem.

Schools have student manual which outlines the school's discipline policies and the code of student conduct. However, despite these established guidelines, some students continue to violate them and their misbehavior is dealt accordingly after multiple conferences and thorough investigation. One way of addressing

pertinent misbehavior is through transfer which is to protect the majority of the learners and considering the possibility that these transferred students may become better and excel in their new school. Additionally, it is often the case that the transfer decision is parent's choice, their own, or the decision of the majority which includes the adviser, subject teachers, coordinators, and other concerned personnel. Transferring students may have been one of the choices as a means to discipline students yet literature present a negative impact of the mentioned disciplinary action.

Lim (2024) mentions that students transfer or mobility often result to adverse and number of barriers as they often adjust to new environment thus leading to lower graduation and college enrollment. As to Dupéré et. al (2022), students transfer to other school leads to a decline in the student's social capital, which in turn led to lower academic performance as well as educational expectations. In addition, as presented by Learning Policy Institute (2023) transferred students leave established social ties behind and find themselves in a foreign land of relationship, expectations, academics, school rules, and procedures.

Another point to consider as American Psychological Association (2021) suggests exclusionary discipline leads to educational disruptions, behavioral and emotional challenges, and high-risk consequences and can contribute to what he termed as the "school to prison pipeline." Turnquest et. al (2024) add that transfer has a long negative, long-term impacts on the mental and school performance of students. A new student may require an early intervention as they may experience

anxiety, anger, unusual withdrawal, academic problems, stress-related reactions. Just one move can be traumatic. Children can react positively or negatively to transfer, they may develop new talents and skills, or they may see this as yet another disruption in their life thus, restorative practices maybe possibly applied such as focusing on developing communication strategies and building relationships (Learning Policy Institute, 2023).

Significantly, a growing body of literature highlights the negative effects of student transfers from one school to another; however, there is a scarcity of studies offering concrete strategies to address these issues. The hope is that through this research, schools will find better solutions to address behavioral problems, thus helping misbehaved students, decrease number of students being transferred leading to a reduction of drop-outs, and contributing to the number of students progressing to the next level and ultimately graduating.

Central to this study is the in-depth exploration of the experiences of transfer students. Significantly, it examines the experiences of students who were transferred to other school due to their misbehavior. The result can also be used as a basis to craft policies that govern the transfer of students from one school to another during the school year, ensuring the protection of the concerned learner without compromising the interest of the majority of the students.

Theoretical Underpinnings of the Study

This study is underpinned into various theories that integrates psychology, sociology, and educational lenses. These theories help in examining whether

transferring students with behavioral cases serves as a solution or to further exclusion.

Erikson's Psychosocial Development Theory together with other psychologist highlights that adolescence is very crucial in human development. It is in this level where self-identity is reinforced and continues to be formed (Cherry, 2023). As supported by Al-Hendawi (2022), student's transfers during this stage can disrupt the social structures where they are used too, undermining self-esteem and increasing behavioral problem. When psychosocial needs such as acceptance and connectedness are unmet, students may internalize rejection, resulting in continued or intensified misbehavior (González & García, 2024).

Complementing the above view is Bronfenbrenner's Ecological Systems Theory, which the interconnected environmental systems start from the immediate to broader societal structure influence a student's behavior. Thus, a student's actions are shaped not only in the family, but also by interactions within school, peer groups, and the broader societal context (Jalbuna & Estoconing, 2024). Student's transfer affects their relation with their environment leading to an interruption in steadiness and support. Transitions can further isolate the student that may reinforce maladaptive behavior (Longobardi et al., 2019).

In a sociological perspective, the Social Control Theory emphasizes that strong social bonds to institutions like schools prevent deviant behavior (Cui et.al, 2024). But if the student perceives the transfer as punishment they will behave differently. Likewise, Wilkins et. al (2023) agree that behavioral misconduct often

worsens when students feel disconnected from school and without support in the new environment, their behavioral issues may escalate.

The Restorative Justice Theory offers an alternative disciplinary framework that promotes healing, accountability, and community reintegration rather than punitive exclusion (Darling, 2023). It is believed that when restorative practices are done in school this encourage an open communication between students, teachers, and other personnel and trust can be rebuild. Studies have shown that behavioral outcomes improve significantly when students are given opportunities to make amends and remain integrated in their communities but without such processes may be disadvantageous (Gregory & Evans, 2020). Subramaniam and Nordin (2025) in a behavioral standpoint based on Skinner's Behaviorism emphasizes that behavior is shaped and largely maintained by reinforcement and consequence. Hence, if students are transferred without exerted support and consistent reinforcement strategies in the new school, behavior may not improve and could worsen. The Care Theory sets in where it stresses the moral responsibility of educators to provide emotional support and continuity, especially to students with problems (Adhikari & Saha, 2023).

Lastly, the Constructivist Learning Theory emphasizes that through social interaction students build understanding and growth (LXD Learning Experience Design, n.d.). It is crucial that when learners are removed from their previous learning context it must be guaranteed that they will receive support in their new environment for them to thrive both in their academic and behavioral growth.

Collectively, the above theories advocate for all-encompassing and needs-responsive action to student misbehavior. Instead of exclusionary measures, the above theories emphasize the importance of looking at the underlying source of the students' misbehavior looking into their social, emotional, and environmental situation. There is a need for interventions that promote inclusion, positive interaction, and support systems that address students' needs fostering a more compassionate and empowering learning environment.

Framework of the Study

Statement of the Problem

The study looked into the lived-experiences of transfer students. The following questions were used as guides: 1) What are the common behavioral cases committed by students and used as a basis for their transfer to other

schools? 2) What are the challenges faced by the transferred-out students in the school where they were transferred? 3) How are transferred-out students affected emotionally, socially, and academically?

Definition of Terms

Transfer Students are students who moved from their previous school due to behavioral concern reflected by the school's disciplinary or administrative records.

Behavioral Cases documented instances wherein students exhibit disruptive, defiant, or aggressive behavior that interfere learning process that warrant consideration for transfer.

Solution is the transfer of a student with behavioral cases to other school hoping positive outcomes, such as improved behavior, better academic performance, enhanced emotional well-being, and successful adjustment to the new school.

Desolation is the transfer of a student with behavioral cases that leads in negative result like, failing academic performance, emotional distress, worsening behavior, or difficulty integrating into the new school setting.

Student Adjustment the observable changes in the student's academic performance, attendance records, and behavioral records following the transfer.

Chapter 2

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This study employed a qualitative phenomenological research design to capture and explore the lived experiences of students who were transferred due to behavioral issues. Through in-depth interviews, participants shared their personal journeys, including the reasons for their transfer, their experiences in the new school environment, and the impact of the transfer on their academic performance, emotional well-being, and social adjustment.

Source of Data

This study involved ten (10) student participants who transferred out from the same school and grade level within the academic year. The researcher employed convenience sampling to select the participants based on accessibility and willingness to participate. An equal gender distribution was maintained in the sample, with five (5) male and five (5) female students participating in the study. All ten students experienced school transfer during the same school year, with two (2) of them having returned to the school after a brief period of enrollment in another institution.

To supplement the data and provide a broader understanding of the transfer experiences, the researcher also interviewed the parents, grandparents, or legal guardians of the selected students. These additional informants offered insights

into the students' behavioral background, home circumstances, and the reasons influencing the decision to transfer.

Instrumentation and Data Collection

A semi-structured interview was used as the primary data-gathering tool. Participants were asked about their reactions, feelings, and personal experiences related to their transfer to other schools. To ensure convenience the interview questions were delivered in a language familiar to the participants. All interviews were recorded to prevent the loss of essential data. Ethical considerations were observed. Participants were fully informed of the purpose of the study, procedures, and their rights. They were asked to read the transcription to ensure accuracy of the data. Also, a dry-run of the questionnaire was conducted to insure clarity. Written consent was obtained before participation, in accordance with ethical research standards. Confidentiality was strictly maintained, with all data anonymized and identified information were kept confidential.

Analysis of Data

All data were transcribed and interpreted using cool and warm analysis. Data were noted from how the participants answered the questions in the informal personal interview. The results were collated, thematized, and analyzed; thus, the researchers come up with the collective meaning of the transfer students lived experiences. Observations of parents were also transcribed and analyzed.

Chapter 3

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This section presents the narratives of the student participants, detailing the behavioral cases that led their transfer, their initial reactions to the decision, and their experiences in their new schools. It further examines the effect of the transfer on their emotional state, social interactions, and academic performance. The data, derived from transcribed interviews, were systematically thematized and analyzed to uncover recurring patterns and deeper meanings related to their lived experiences. These findings are discussed comprehensively in the succeeding subsections.

Behavioral Cases: Light, less grave, and grave offenses

The following discussion highlights the specific behavioral cases committed by the student participants. The study involved an equal number of male and female participants, comprising five males and five females.

Among the ten participants, three incurred light offenses like; improper haircut, noisy inside and outside the classroom, wearing inappropriate and incomplete uniform. The two students' violation is under less grave offenses such as; habitual tardiness, unnecessary absences, and cutting classes. The other five students are either involved in fighting, disrespect for teachers and fellow students, cheating, extortion, possession, and use of harmful objects, which are all under grave offenses.

Student A is a quiet person, usually mingles with a selected few, incurred excessive absences and demonstrated habitual tardiness. Student B on the other hand, was involved in fighting and allegedly a gang member. In the case of Student C, peer influence played a significant role in truancy. Student D was known for wearing incomplete uniforms, improper haircuts, and cause disruption in class. He was also involved in fighting because of "*masama ang tingin*" (shot a hostile glare) of a classmate. His light offenses were tolerated, but his encounter with one of his classmates prompted the adviser to advise the parent to transfer their son. Student E resides with her grandmother. His record reflects serious disciplinary offenses, including acts of disrespect toward both teachers and classmates.

As for Student F, the transfer decision came from the mother. She has been extorting from her classmates and engaging in self-harming such as wrist cutting. With regard to Student G, persistent absenteeism, chronic tardiness, and displays of disrespect led the adviser to recommend a transfer to a school located closer to the family's residence. Student H opted to transfer, stating that her habitual tardiness and absenteeism were due to transportation challenges in their area. She subsequently sought her mother's support in arranging the transfer. Reports indicated that Student I frequently stayed out at night, which affected her ability to attend school regularly. She returned to her aunt's home only at her own discretion. As the aunt could no longer manage her behavior, she decided to return Student I to her mother's place. Consequently, the student needed to be transferred to another school near her mother's residence. Student J incurred unnecessary absences. According to the child, she needs to do a part-time job because the

mother is not giving them enough allowance. She incurred a lot of absences and missed her academics.

Challenges faced by the transferred-out students

Student behavioral issues are frequently cited as a significant factor influencing school transfers. These transfers may be categorized as family-initiated, student-requested, or school-mandated. Student A after two weeks of stay in the other school he decided to go back to his previous school. Together with the mother, they pleaded to the former adviser to accept him again. The adviser though hesitant, admitted him again. The following are the sharing done during the conversations with the mother and the student.

Student A narrated, *“ayaw ko sana magtransfer kasi sanay na ako sa mga kaklase ko pero sabi ni mama subukan ko sa ibang school”*. (If possible, I don't want to transfer, but my mother said I would try other schools.) The mother of Student A processed the transfer paper for his transfer but after two weeks they pleaded to his former adviser to accept him again in his class. According to the student his adviser asked him, *“bakit ka babalik e nagtransfer na nga? (Why will you come back you already transferred?)”*. But they insist and persist and his former adviser accepted him again. Basing on the interview it was evident that Student A brought along with him the problem that he had in the previous school.

In the case of Student B, the mother disclosed that the student did not pursue the transfer and had ultimately discontinued his schooling. The transfer of students B was the decision of the father to protect his child and prevent a further

encounter with the other student whom he had a brawl. He said during the conference' "*volunteer ko na magtransfer siya para hindi sila magkikita ng nakaaway niya at baka may mangyari ulit sa kanila* (I volunteer his transfer to prevent further encounters with the student he had a conflict with, as there was concern that another incident might occur.)" The mother shared that her son was so hesitant of the conferences' result and of his father's decision but cannot do anything but to follow his father.

In the case of Student C, the father after the parent-student-teacher conference, decided to transfer his child. "*I-transferko mam para malayo siya sa kanyang mga barkada* (I will transfer him so he will be far from his friends)." Though the student at first was hesitant, he agreed at the end. The father added that he further explained the decision to his child. During the follow-up interview on the student's situation, the father was so delighted to share his child's improvement. Student C pointed out that at first, he was hard up to adjust with his classmates and his teachers, and still meet his old friends but with his father's persistent in guiding him he was able to adjust. "*Mabait din mga teachers doon at tinulungan ako na matapos mga hindi ko nagawa* (my teachers there are kind and they help me to finish the works that I missed)." Family support is of great importance in the survival of the students (Marley & Wilcox, 2022). Moreover, school accommodation is a significant factor when students are effectively supported, it greatly enhances their chances of succeeding in their new school environment (Felten, 2021).

Student D initially exhibited reluctance to transfer, expressing concern about being separated from his peers and the familiarity of his current teacher.

However, his mother remained firm in the decision to enroll him in a new school. Although he initially struggled with classroom behavior particularly due to his talkativeness, which often drew the teacher's attention his academic performance showed noticeable improvement. According to his mother, his talkative nature is part of his personality. Though his outgoing disposition helped facilitated a smoother adjustment process, allowing him to adapt more easily to his new school environment.

On student E's case, the grandmother was bitter in reporting that the child opts not to continue his studies. *Pinipilit naming mag enrol doon sa ibang school pero ayaw talaga* (we convinced him to enroll in other school but he doesn't really like)." When student E was asked why he didn't transfer to another school, he said: "*wala lang* (nothing)" and ended the conversation. The grandmother expressed sympathy for her grandson but admitted feeling powerless to change the situation. Student E's grandmother reported that he no longer expresses a desire to attend school, leading her to consider reenrollment in the following school year, if her grandson is willingness. Having cared for Student E since infancy, the grandmother acknowledged persistent challenges in disciplining him, which may have contributed to his current disengagement from schooling.

The grandmother always complains "*noon sa mga anak ko kahit minsan di ako pinatawag ng guro, siya talaga ang nagbibigay sa akin ng sakit ng ulo* (for my children I have never been called by the teachers not even once, he is always giving me a headache)." His grandson in the interview was asked why he have such behavior doesn't want to engage in the conversation and preferred to be

quiet. Individuals who lack adequate supportive relationships, particularly from family members, are at a higher risk of experiencing more pronounced negative effects on their life (Carvalho et. al, 2025).

Student F shared: *nahirapan kasi ako mag adjust sa mga kaklase ko hinahanap hanap ko pa rin mga kasama ko sa school ko dati, pero nakapasa naman ako at mababait din naman guro ko doon* (I am hard up in adjusting with my new classmates, I miss my former classmates, although I passed, and my teachers there are also kind).” Student also related that at first, she felt so all alone because she doesn’t know anyone but soon was able to find a friend and makes him feel welcomed in his new school. According to Yi et. al (2023) when a student feels they belong, it can promote interest, enthusiasm, and increase their willingness to engage in academic activities.

The mother of Student G agreed to transfer her child: *transfer ko mam don sa private school na malapit sa amin ta medjo mabantayanko, nandito ate nya pero di nya mabantayan ta nasa grade 9* (I will transfer her in the private school near us, the sister is here but she cannot look after her because she is in grade 9).” On the follow-up on the student’s situation in her new school the mother said: *mam, pumasok doon ng wala atang isang linggo pero pagkatapos non ayaw na pumasok kasi nahihirapan daw mag adjust sa subject at di nauunawaan ang mga dinidiscuss ng guro* (she attended for less than a week, but after that, she no longer wanted to go to school because she said she was having a hard time adjusting to the subjects and could not understand what the teacher was discussing.).”

After a week of stay in other school Student H together with the mother pleads for her return. The mother shared that the adviser was so upset, yet again accommodated Student H. When the mother was interviewed why she returned: *ayaw na daw niya don mam kasi di na daw pumapasok kasama niya na nagtransfer at nahihirapan daw din siya don mam, nahihirapan daw siyang intindihin ang mga lesson nya* (she doesn't want there anymore because her friend who was her companion who transferred there is no longer entering her class, and she was also hard up there, she was hard up in understanding her lesson)."

The anecdotal record of Student I indicates that her behaviors fall under grave offenses, including documented instances of misconduct occurring outside the school premises. She currently resides with her aunt, who serves as her legal guardian. During the interview, the aunt expressed strong frustration and dissatisfaction toward the student and declined to provide her contact number, limiting opportunities for further interviews and follow-up discussions but at the end she mentioned that the child opted not to continue her studies.

Student J's mother was shocked to know that her child was not entering her class. So, upon conferences the mother decided to transfer her to other school so she will be monitored, but basing from the advisers report they didn't process the transfer and the child decided to drop. The researcher tried to followed up but the student and the mother are no longer cooperating. There should have been other concerns that need to be addressed but due to uncooperativeness and disinterest also of the parents the child instead didn't continue her studies. Students have personal concerns that often times advisers and teachers don't

have the capacity to look at it deeply due to time constraint and lack of cooperation of both parties.

The transfer students were affected in many various ways. Often times they are hard up adjusting to their new environment, to their classmates, system of the school where they transferred and on the styles of their teachers. Also, they need to deal with the teachers, school system, subjects, and their new environment.

The emotional, social, and academic effect of transfer to students

Among those interviewed, only one student expressed enthusiasm about her transfer, and she was the sole individual who initiated the move on her own accord. Nine students have varied emotions: sad, upset, hesitant, angry, frustrated, dismayed, and one was hesitant to open up his situation. Some of the reason for the emotions were: they are used to their classmates and hard to leave old friends, the decision wasn't fair, cannot go against the decision of their parents, worried about what wait in the other school, still questions the reason why they need to be transferred, and one is in denial on what is happening.

Transferred-out students have varied reactions on their transfer and on the result of the study most of them were able to move on were not able to make it for the school year. The following narrates how they were affected emotionally, socially, and academically as a result of their transfer. The following were what transpired during the interview and conversations with the students and parents.

Student A narrated, *"nalungkot po ako nong sinabihan ako ng adviserko na magtransfer na lang ako sa ibang school"*. (When my adviser advised me to transfer, I feel sad because I am already used to my classmates. In the interview

Student A was asked why he came back, he answered, *“ayoko don mam kasi feel ko hindi ako welcome, palagi ako pinaririrangan ng adviser ko doon na ‘lahat present isa lang wala’ kaya kinausap namin ni mama si mam na babalik ako. (I don’t feel comfortable going back there, ma’am, because I don’t feel welcomed. My adviser often makes indirect remarks like, ‘Everyone is present except one.’ That’s why my mom and I spoke with ma’am and decided that I would transfer back.)”*. Thus, the adviser accepted Student A again, and he was able to pass and finished his grade seven. Bryan et.al (2020) states that after a student enters the new classroom, the communication between the counselor and student, the counselor and the teachers, and the student and teacher is crucial. Felten (2021) emphasized that teachers can assist with transfer students by being cognizant and alert to signs of distress or success. The teacher is generally responsible for the progress of all students in the class, for diagnosing academic problems and meeting individual learning needs. In looking at students concern and personal distress they may be assisted properly which may lead to their success. The decision of the former adviser to readmit the previously disengaged student was instrumental in providing targeted support that facilitated the student’s academic recovery and advancement.

When student B was interviewed through the phone patch, shared that he didn’t feel like going to other school and brought out his sentiments *“ma’am ba’t daw ako kailangang itransfer dapat tinerransfer din ninyo si student K para patas at hindi lang ako ang nadiin (Ma’am why do I need to be transferred, you should have transferred Student K too so it is even and I am not the only one in blame).”*

The student was so hesitant to transfer but the father insisted. *“Unfair naman kasi mam parang ako lang naman may kasalanan (it is unfair mam it seems am the only at fault).”* The student was not convinced of the decision; he wanted that his school mate whom he had encounter should also be transferred to other school. He feels being eyed upon and the blame is only towards him. Yet, the conferences were well moderated and the decision was approved by those concerned. But the student was not satisfied and insist of the unfairness of the decision and decided not to continue his studies.

In the case of Student C, he was hesitant of the decision yet he agreed at the end. The father was so delighted to share his child's improvement. *“Naging maayos naman na siya madam, maayos na din makitungo sa amin, napalayo siya sa kanyang barkada. Tumaas din ang grades niya (He is already ok, he deals with us properly, he was detached from his friends and his grades improved).”* Children respond to the situation in various ways and family support is of great importance in the survival of the students. The father’s support to his son abled the child to move on and engage himself in his studies and was able to surpass his limitations which abled him to finish level up to the next grade level.

Mother of Student D was determined to transfer her son to another school. The result was good Student D was able to pass his academics, but his being talkative and noisy in the classroom is still the complaint of his teachers as shared by the mother. We differ in many different ways and our differences makes us unique that helps us to achieve what we want.

After few months of his transfer, student E's schooling was followed up but the grandmother was so bitter in reporting that the child opts not to continue his studies. Student E's grandmother in the interview brought out her sentiment: "*mam hanggang ngayon masakit talaga loob ko bakit palagi na lang ang apo ko nakikita lalong-lalo yong adviser, mahirap magtransfer kasi. Naaawa ako sa apo ko pero wala na ako magawa at talagang ayaw na niya mag-aral ulit. Sa susunod na lang na pasukan kung gusto niya, inasa na kasi ng magulang niya yan sa akin mahirap ko siyang idisiplina hindi kagaya ng ibang apoko.* (Until now I don't feel good because they are always eyeing at my grandson specially the adviser, it's hard to transfer. I pity my grandson but I can't do anything, his parents leave him to me. I will enroll him this coming school year if he wants, he is very different, I am hard in disciplining him.)

Student E was devastated due to the transfer decision. His situation was also much affected by the absence of his parents and as sensed from the conferences with the grandmother, he is always compared to his siblings. The grandmother always complains on her grandson's behavior. Student E in most of the conferences was just quiet and often didn't react on the conversations and seem doesn't even care of the decision.

In the case of Student F her mother shared that she passed but her grades went down, hard-up adjusting with her classmates, and in catching up with her lessons. There was even a time she almost wants to drop but when she befriended a classmate this enticed her to go to school every day. Though she still missed her former teachers and classmates she was able to make it.

Student G was not interviewed because, according to the mother, she doesn't want to talk to the researcher. The mother just narrated: *nahihiya daw siya doon, kakaiba mga kaklase pati mga guro at hindi na makahabol sa mga topics...yon mam basta na lang ayaw pumasok at doon palagi na lang tulog, gusto niya palagi mag-isa, kakaiba talaga ang anak ko na ito hindi ko alam ang gusto ang ate di naman ganun pag may gusto sabihin sinasabi naman sa akin pero siya halos ayaw magsalita* (she is shy, the students there are so different even the teachers and she cannot cope up with the lessons, and she doesn't really want to enter already. She is there always sleeping and always wants to be alone. She is really so different; I don't know what she wants, she is so different from her sister and she even barely talks)."

Student H reported that she was initially encouraged by a peer to transfer and subsequently expressed her apologies to the adviser. However, following her peer's withdrawal, she experienced feelings of isolation and lacked social support. She asked her mother to talk to her adviser from her previous school to accept her again. Though at first the former adviser was hesitant to accept her again but at the end she accepted her again and was able to make it with good grades.

The situation of student I was gathered from her aunt-guardian. The aunt shared of her dislike of her niece's behavior and decided to stop supporting her in her studies. With the sharing done with the adviser the child wasn't really happy being with the aunt and doesn't feel going home and prefer to stay outside and be with her friends. In the follow-up interview the aunt reported that the child didn't continue the transfer and decided to drop.

Student J claimed that she needed to work because her mother was not supporting her financially thus incurring numerous absences. But in the interview with the mother, she was unawareness of her child absences. The mother arranged the transfer hoping it would help her daughter focus and continue her studies; however, the student ultimately chose not to proceed and discontinued her schooling.

Basing on the documented interview, two students (Student A and H) went back to their previous school after a few weeks of stay in the school where they transferred. Four (Students B, E, I, and J) didn't continue or didn't process the transfer, two improved (Students C and D), one said her grades went down (Student F), and one (Student G) entered the school of her parent's choice but soon dropped. As a result, among ten participants, five students were able to pass and moved on the next level. One didn't survive in the school where she transferred, and four preferred not to continue their studies. Also, most of them showed negative emotions or reactions in response to the transfer decision.

This study shows that out of the ten respondents, two showed positive emotions, but eight students described negative reactions. Students differ in their ability and capability to cope with the situation they encounter, often times there are students who can adapt easily and there are those who can't and ended up disoriented or unsuccessful due to wide range of emotions including loneliness, fear, embarrassment, and anxiety.

Chapter 4

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

Summary

Among the ten students who were interviewed, only one student showed excitement of the transfer while the remaining nine showed negative emotions. The students manifested hesitancy, dismay, anger, sadness, and frustration. Their negative reactions is a result to unfamiliarity of the new school, unknown people, look into the decision as unfair, no choice, and separation from friends.

Emotional and social Reaction:

- Most of the interviewed students felt unwelcomed, isolated, or not treated fairly in their new schools.
- Students, A and H, who lack social support and emotionally distress returned to their original school after a short period.
- Students B, E, I, and J did not continue their studies, because of unresolved emotional issues, lack of family support, and disinterest.
- Students C and D showed behavioral improvement after their transfer.
- Student F struggled with adjustment until she was able to adjust especially when she made friends.
- Student G was hard up in adjusting so he dropped.

Academic Outcomes:

- With family strong support, students C and D showed academic improvement after transfer.

- Student F passed but had lower grades.
- Student G dropped out shortly after transferring.

Family Support:

- Strong family support resulted to positive outcomes and adjustment.
- Students who were not well supported, have unresolved emotional conflicts, and have doubts on the decision showed negative outcomes.
- There are parents and guardians who expressed difficulty in disciplining the children under their care.

Final Outcome:

- 5 students passed and moved to the next grade.
- 4 students dropped out or did not pursue transfer.
- 1 student enrolled but failed to adjust and dropped out.

Findings

This study analyzed the transfer outcome of the students with their behavioral cases. Thus, the following were the findings of the study:

1. Categorization of Offenses: Light and less grave offenses led to grave offenses that results to various consequences.
2. Emotional Reactions: Negative emotions like sadness, frustration, and anger were evident from the nine (9) participants.
3. Adaptation Result: Students who were strongly guided by family improved academically. Others preferred or not to continue their transfer due to lack of support, poor social adjustment and other issues.

4. Family Support: Family support is crucial in student's recovery and success but absence of such support led to frustration and dropped-out.

Conclusion

The interpretation of data assisted the researchers to conclude that:

1. Grave and escalated behavioral offenses contributed to transfer decision.
2. Schools' emotional concern and empathy is substantial to students encountering sadness, frustration, and anger.
3. Support and guidance of family members are crucial for the success of transfer process and result.
4. Students with engaged families tend to overcome challenges better.

The study suggests rounded school interventions, including early monitoring of behavior, unsuppressed student involvement in decision-making, and strong school-family collaboration, to support at-risk students and promote sustainable development among transferred students.

Recommendation

The following result-focused strategies are recommended to schools as a response to the behavioral and academic challenges faced by students undergoing school transfer.

1. Create a Behavioral Risk Identification Tool

Institutionalization of a standardized instrument for identifying students at risk of behavioral issues. A tool that should include teachers' feedback, guidance counselor assessments, and behavioral tracking systems to cut down light offenses before they develop into less grave or grave violations.

2. Establish a Student Transfer Support Framework

A structured program which includes pre-transfer counselling sessions that includes the student and family, orientation program in the school they transferred, and monitoring for at least one academic quarter.

3. Enhance School-Family Collaboration Mechanisms

To strengthen partnership between school and parents the following may be followed: Assigning case adviser for students with behavioral records, conduct of quarterly family conferences, and seminars for parents on behavioral management.

4. Deploy Peer and Teacher Mentorship Programs

Identify supportive faculty members to peer mentor students who are identified with behavioral offenses. This approach will provide emotional support, promote social belongingness, and a welcoming school climate.

5. Monitor and Evaluate Transfer Outcomes

Assigned peer mentor regularly monitor academic, emotional, and behavioral progress of students assigned to them. Regularly check on progress reports from advisers.

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